

Evaluating the Physical, Socio-Economic and Psychological Consequences of Traditional Bone Setter Practices: A Community-Based Appraisal in Kano State

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ABSTRACT- *The study aimed at evaluating the physical, socio-economic, and psychological consequences following complications of traditional bone-setting interventions among infants/youths with simple fractures/trauma on their future livelihood in Kano metropolis, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted, with a sample size of 120 community respondents drawn from four (4) of the metropolitan local government areas of the state using an accidental sampling procedure. A researcher-based Questionnaire- 'Community members' opinion assessment on traditional bone setters' interventions questionnaire, (CMOATBSQ), and Community members' opinion assessment on traditional bone setters' interventions Focus Group Discussion Checklist Guide (CMOATBSFGD), were developed, validated, and administered accordingly. Frequency tables and percentages were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed multiple complications that usually result from TBSs' interventions, ranging from non-union, mal-union, soft tissue injuries, bone infections, and amputations, leading to ultimate dependency, and their subsequent physical, economic, social, and psychological trauma on the lives of the victims, among others. Despite these, TBSs were nonetheless being patronized for various reasons. A need for public awareness creation among the populace, using all the available means and media, becomes imperative with a view to preventing or minimizing this abnormal consequence. This can be done through a series of engagements, symposiums/workshops, and mutual respect for one another, among others.*

Keywords: Fracture, trauma, infants/youths, complications, consequences, Media

I. Introduction

Traditional bone setting (TBS) practice is an important part of health care delivery in many developing countries and has been in Nigeria for a long time (Aderibigbe et al., 2013). A traditional bonesetter (TBS) is a lay practitioner of joint manipulation (Salihu et al., 2021). The practice of traditional bone setting is recognized as a specialized method of traditional medicine, and the expertise is perceived to be passed within the same family. However, interested individuals outside the family can be trained through apprenticeship (Jibo et al., 2021). Although the traditional bone setting (TBS) is still in existence despite all the criticism and adversities.¹ Bone setting practices contribute largely to alternative medicine almost all over the world (more especially in the context of Asia, Africa, and South America) (Salihu et al., 2021).

It's commonly accessible in large parts of rural populations (Odatuwa-Omagbemi, David Odoyoh Adiki, Thomas Odafe Elachi, Cornelius Itodo Bafo, 2018). He or she is a practitioner who takes up the practice of healing without having had any formal training in accepted medical procedures (Green, 1999). Since TBS lacks the basic principles of infection control in wound management, their intervention in the treatment of open fractures is bound to be associated with complications (Salihu, Lawal, Adigun and Muhammad, 2022). Omololu, Ogunlade & Gopaldasani (2008), in their study, 'The Practice of Traditional Bone setting Training Algorithm', found out that, lack of knowledge of anatomy, physiology, radiology and basic principles of infection prevention and control and soft tissue care, leads or results to limb and other life-threatening complications

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which range from acute compartment syndrome, tetanus, deformities, chronic osteomyelitis, gangrene, amputation and death. These complications equally become a major concern with regard to morbidity and mortality (Oladiran, Adeniran, 2001). Machaku, Lodhia, Nangole, Kondo, and Massawe (2025), also discovered that, while TBSs are sometimes chosen for affordability and cultural reasons, this frequently results in severe complications like gangrene, non-union, osteomyelitis, limb shortening, or even death. Many failures of bone setting procedures have been reported, leading to a bad reputation for the providers (Agawal and Agawal, 2010). Despite the complications that arise from the cultural practice, TBS services still remain in high demand by a significant number of people (Aderibigbe et al., 2013). According to an estimate, only between 10 to 40% of patients with fractures and dislocations in the world are managed by unorthodox practitioners (Green, 1999). In a study conducted by Singaram and Naido (2019), it was found that long bone fractures have a considerable impact on many facets of a patient's life, including preventing patients from working and meeting financial obligations, limiting previously normal social interactions, and pre-injury functions. In a similar study conducted by Machaku, Lodhia, Nangole, Kondo and Massawe (2025), it was equally discovered that, traditional bone setting interventions lead to significant negative social and economic consequences for clients, including permanent disabilities, loss of income, increased healthcare costs due to managing complications, and social stigma, with a proportionate impact on young people who are often disabled during their productive years, thereby transforming initial injuries into life-long burdens for the affected individuals and their families. Such consequences include social (leading to disability and deformity, social stigma-exclusion, discrimination, loss of social status- due to inability to participate in activities or work), psychological trauma (due to severe pains, disability and resultant social changes leading to distress to the client and their family). In a similar study conducted by Singaram and Naido (2019), they also found that long bone fractures have a considerable impact on many facets of a patient's life, including preventing patients from working and meeting financial obligations, limiting previously normal social interactions, and pre-injury functions. It is on this note that the researcher intends to evaluate the social, economic, and psychological consequences that follow complications from

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traditional bonesetters' interventions in the area of the study.

II. Traditional Practice

We visited a traditional bonesetter in order to document his clinic sessions, consultations, and treatment of fractures. The first step for the TBS is to identify a fracture, which is accomplished by noting the following symptoms and signs: swelling, pain, loss of function, angulations, abnormal mobility, and crepitus on palpation of the fracture site (Omololu, A. B., MD, Ogunlade, FRCS, S. O. Gopaldasani, 2008).

Figure 1: Fracture

Source: (Omololu, A. B. MD Ogunlade FRCS, S. O. Gopaldasani, 2008).

III. Aim for the Study

The aim of the study is to determine the physical, socio-economic, and psychological consequences resulting from the traditional bone setting intervention complications among infants/youths with simple fractures/trauma on their future livelihood.

IV. Methodology

A survey design questionnaire totaling 120 community members from the Kano metropolitan areas was sampled using an accidental sampling procedure. This was augmented with a focus group discussion checklist. Frequency and percentage tables were used to analyze the data.

V. Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Community Respondents

Variable	Value	Percentage
Age		
18-29	23	19.2
30-39	39	32.5
40-49	48	40
50 & above	10	8.3
Total	120	100
Sex		
Male	103	85.8
Female	17	14.2
Total	120	100
Marital Status		
Married	83	69.2
Single	32	26.7
Divorced	1.0	0.8
Widowed	4.0	3.3
Others(specify)	0.0	0.0
Total	120	100
Education		
Qur'anic	35	29.2
Primary	14	11.7
Basic Literacy	11	9.2
Primary	14	11.6
Secondary	24	20
Tertiary	22	18.3
Others(specify)	0.0	0.0
Total	120	100
Occupation		
Civil servant	48	40
Trader	36	30
Farmer	15	12.5
Others (specify)	21	17.5
Total	120	100

Table 1: The demographic characteristics of the community members' respondents.

The majority of the respondents 48(40%) fall within the age bracket of 40-49 years, 103(85.8%) males, 83(69.2%) married, 35(29.2%), attended Qur'anic education, and

48(40%) civil servants. What are the basic complications following traditional bone setting interventions among infants/youth with simple fractures/trauma?

Table 2: Showing community responses on Basic problems/complications observed among individuals with fractures/trauma following traditional bone setting interventions.

Variable	Value	Percentage
Does any of family member suffered from simple fracture/trauma		
Yes	38	31.7
No	82	68.3
Others	0.0	0.0
Total	120	100

If the above answer is yes, how old is the person at the time of the injury?

6 months -3 years	2.0	1.7
4 -6 years	12	10
7 -10 years	36	30
11-13 years	27	22.5
14-18 years Others, (specify)	43	35.8
Total	120	100

Variable	Value	Percentage
Is the Person male or female		
Male	91	75.8
Female	29	24.2
Others (specify)	0.0	0.0
Total	120	100

Following the fracture/trauma, where was the client he/her taken to for treatment?

To the hospital	27	22.5
Family members treated him/her	6.0	5.0
To the traditional bone-setter	87	72.5
Others, (specify)	0.0	0.0
Total	120	100

If client is treated by TBS, has the client healed properly?

Yes	38	31.7
No	77	64.2
Others (specify)	6	4.1
Total	120	100

If the answer above is no, what complication(s) did the client experienced?

The bones fail to unite (non-union)	31	25.8
The bones appear on the surface of the skin (exposed bone fragments)	3.0	2.5
The bones unite in an abnormal position (mal-union)	77	64.2
The site of the fracture begins to discharge (infection)	4	3.3
The limb becomes rotten (gangrene)	3	2.5
Others (specify)	2	1.7
Total	120	100

Variable	Value	Percentage
What is the implication of the above complications on the life of the client?		
⇒ The client became disabled following the loss of the limb	27	22.5
⇒ The client is separated from other members of the community due to abnormal discharge from the fractured site	5.0	4.2
⇒ The client became dependent on other family members due to disability	21	17.5
⇒ The client is psychologically disturbed	14	11.7
⇒ All of the above	53	44.2
⇒ Others, (specify)	0.0	0.0
Total	120	100.1

Following the above experience, in your own opinion, do you think the TBSs are qualifying enough to be treating infants/youths with simple fractures/trauma in your community?

Yes	57	47.5
No	60	50
Others(specify)	3.0	2.4
Total	120	99.9

Source: Field Data, 2025

Table 2 Responses on the complications and the subsequent physical, social, economic, and psychological consequences on future livelihood are usually observed among clients who undergone TBSs' interventions. Nine items were arranged to seek the respondents' responses. On whether a member of a family has ever sustained fracture/trauma, majority of the respondents, (82,68.3%) are affirmative, only 38 (31.7%) answered no, and majority of the clients (43, 35.8% fell within the age bracket of 14-18years), with 91(75.8%), being males as against 29 (24.2 %) being females. This indicates that the high prevalence of traumatic injuries affects the boys more than the girls in the area under study. As a preference for intervention, only 27(22.5%), decided to take the victim to the hospital (probably due to residing in metropolitan areas) for experts' management, as against 87(72.5%) that opted for TBS interventions. Only 6 clients (5%) were said to have been treated by family members, meaning that the client may have fallen as a member of the TBSs themselves, and therefore took it upon themselves to

intervention. As regards whether the client healed following the TBSs intervention, the majority of the respondents, 77(64.2%), answered no, with only 38(31.7%) answering yes. Only 6 respondents (5%) responded on 'others', which ranged from no healing initially, until after the second attempt, or family members had to seek alternatives. Responding on the complications following the failure of the fracture healing, majority 77(64.2%), reported that the fracture united in an abnormal position (mal-union), 31(25.8%), reported non-union, 3(2.5%), gangrene, 3(2.5%), bone exposed on the surface of the skin and 4(3.3%) reported infection. Only 2 respondents (1.7%) mentioned 'others', which include loss of function of the injured limb, the skin assumed a different texture (discoloration), presumably due to ischemia,

which luckily, did not result in gangrene. Responding on the psycho-social and emotional consequences following the complications observed on the life of the victims, majority, 53 respondents (44.2%), mentioned on 'all of the above', which ranges from; the client became disabled due to either loss of limb, dis-function, infection and psychological disturbance as against 27(22.5%), 21(17.5%), 14(11.7,) and(4.2%) that mentioned the person became disabled, dependent, psychologically disturbed and separated from the community respectively. (The 100.1% is due to rounding error). This is an indication that physical, social, and psychological consequences are enormous, resulting from TBS's interventions. Responding to whether the TBSs should be patronized despite the complications/consequences observed, the majority (60,50.0%) said no, while 57 (47.5%) responded yes. Only 3 (2.4%) mentioned 'others', which gave a double opinion. Responding to reasons for the 'yes' choice, answers range from: they are accessible, and cheap, among others, while those for 'no' choice, responses range from: 'they cause more havoc, and psychological disturbance, among others. (The 99.9% is due to rounding error).

VI. Discussion

Findings relating to basic complications that are usually experienced following traditional bone setting interventions among infant/youth with simple fracture/trauma revealed the majority of the respondents 77(64.2%) mentioned that the bones failed to unite (mal-union), 31(25.8%), mentioned non-union, 4,(3.3%), and3,(2.5%), and 3(2.5%)mentioned the limb begins to discharge (infection), and becomes rotten(gangrene) and bone appeared on the surface on the skin respectively. This finding is similar to that of Onyemaech, Onwuasoigwe, Nwankwo, Schuh, and Popoola (2014), (Onyemaechi, Ndubuisi, OC Lasebikan, Omolade A. Elachi, Itodo C. Popoola (2015), who in their study entitled, 'Complications of musculoskeletal injuries treated by traditional bone setters in a developing country', found out

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that complications following TBSs' interventions include, acute compartment syndrome, non-union, mal-union, joint stiffness, contractures, chronic osteomyelitis (infection), Volkmann's ischemic contractures, gangrene, and death. The finding is also in line with that of Oladiran and Adeniran (2001), who equally said that these complications, which range from acute compartment syndrome, tetanus, deformities, chronic osteomyelitis, gangrene, amputation, and death, are life-threatening and have become a major concern with regard to morbidity and mortality. The finding is also in line with that of Machaku, Lodhia, Nangole, Kondo and Massawe (2025), who in a study entitled, 'Loss of Limb: A consequence of traditional bone-setting', often lead to complications, such as non-union, mal-union, infection, compartment syndrome, and even limb amputation (Machaku, Lodhia, Nangole, Kondo and Massawe (2025)). In a focus group discussion, a family member narrating the ordeal that led to the amputation of the lower limb of one of his siblings, said the fracture was initially open, despite his plea for expert intervention, other relatives insisted and convinced him that the limb might be amputated if they dared go to the hospital. In a similar discussion elsewhere, a victim's relation highlighting on the development of gangrene, said that, initially, the patient seriously complained of persistent and severe pain at the site of the reduced and immobilized fracture site, but no intervention was initiated from them (the family members), or reported the the TBS, which later became rotten, and subsequently led to the loss of the patient's limb. Equally, those who experienced discharge from the site of the fractured site said that, initially, the fractured bone appeared on the skin (compound fracture), despite that, they still took him to the TBS for intervention, resulting in the complication. This is a pointer that, despite the long time experienced by TBSs in their respective practices, undesirable consequences are still associated with their interventions. To this end, and indeed, since the TBSs play an important role in the management of fractures/trauma among infants/youths, consideration should be made to curtail these unfortunate incidences of complications among members of the communities. On the socio-economic and psychological effects of the TBSs interventions, majority of the respondents, majority, (53, 44.2%), mentioned on 'all of the above', which ranges from; the client became disabled due to

either loss of limb, dis-function, infection and psychological disturbance as against 27(22.5%), 21 (17.5%), 14(11.7,) and(4.2%) that mentioned the person became disabled, dependent, psychologically disturbed and separated from the community respectively. The socio-psychological consequences following TBS interventions are therefore equally multiple, creating dependency due to loss of limb, and frustration as a result of stigmatization and separation from other members of society. This finding is also similar to that of Machaku, Lodhia, Nangole, Kondo, and Massawe (2025), who observed, 'while TBSs are sometimes chosen for affordability and cultural reasons, it frequently results in severe complications like gangrene, non-union, osteomyelitis, limb shortening, or even death, transforming initial injuries into life-long burdens for the affected individuals and their families. In a similar study conducted by Singaram and Naido (2019), also found that long bone fractures have a considerable impact on many facets of a patient's life, including preventing patients from working and meeting financial obligations, limiting previously normal social interactions, and pre-injury functions

VII. Conclusion

In line with the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that there is a lot to be done to improve the performance of the TBSs in order to minimize or prevent the undesirable consequences that usually follow their interventions. Steps to be taken will among others include, but not limited to, improving and paying absolute attention concerning knowledge acquisition, methods and techniques of reduction and immobilization of fracture (to be more scientific), improving and paying considerable attention on their knowledge of basic human anatomy and physiology and principles of infection prevention and control, and recognition of the need for mutual respect and dignity for each other. These steps were equally considered and implemented with the traditional birth attendants, and a lot has been achieved in their performances in preventing and reducing maternal and perinatal deaths in the communities.

VIII. Recommendations

- A kind of synergy/collaboration should be established between the orthodox healthcare practitioners and the TBSs with government support, to complement each other based on

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capacity, respect, and mutual understanding, with a view to easing tension between the two parties and preventing complications.

- Government and other stakeholders should employ measures directed at improving formal education through adult literacy programs with a view to enhancing TBSs literacy levels and awareness creation that will impact their performances in the community.
- Orthodox healthcare practitioners, with government support, should develop techniques and strategies towards modernizing the TBS's crude and unscientific ways of treating fractures/trauma to scientific and more sterile methods through seminars and workshops with a view to preventing sepsis or infection.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the study Conceptualization and design. Garba, Tijjani Alhaji, performed material preparation and Methodology, writing the original draft, Analysis of results, data collection, and analysis. Muhammad Muhammad Suleiman was instrumental in acquiring observations and contributed relevant expertise, proofreading, and formatting the manuscript. All authors commented on previous versions, read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest

The author(s) declare that they have no known competing financial interests, professional affiliations, or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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